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A GIANT OVARIAN JUVENILE GRANULOSA CELL TUMOUR IN AN ADOLESCENT FEMALES: AN UNCOMMON CASE PRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Ovarian sex cord stromal tumours include neoplasms that derive from granulosa cells, Seroi cells, theca cells, Leyding cells and fibroblasts of gonadal stromal origin. We present patient C., aged 15, was admitted with a 12-month history of periodic abdominal pain, abdominal enlargement and amenorrhea. Menarche from 14 years of age, previously normal menstrual cycle, sexually active since 14 years of age, which led the patient to believe she was pregnant. After preoperative preparation, surgery was performed with a left transrectal laparotomy. On revision, a massive tumor formation was found, originating from the left ovary without involving adjacent organs and anatomical structures. Radical resection of the tumor was performed with the fallopian tube.

The results of histopathological examination established the presence of juvenile type granulosa tumor, provisional stage pT1a, high mitotic activity (mitotic rate 40 in 10 fields of view), moderate nuclear atypia and extensive foci of necrosis. The tumor infiltrated tubular tissue in which foci of necrosis and tumor foci of juvenile type granulosa cells were present.

The patient was discharged in satisfactory condition and referred to an oncology institution to determine further treatment tactics.

Keywords: Ovarian Tumor, granulosa cell tumor, adolescent.

Ovarian sex cord stromal tumours include neoplasms that derive from granulosa cells, Seroi cells, theca cells, Leyding cells and fibroblasts of gonadal stromal origin (Hashemipour M. et al., 2010).

Granulosa cell tumours, described in detail by Scully R.E. (1977), are ovarian stromal neoplasms of the sex cord, which represent about 2-5% of all ovarian tumours [13]. In children they occur extremely rarely, with a reported incidence of 0.1% of all ovarian tumours. Only 4-5% of granuloma cell tumours are seen in children [10, 16]. Two subtypes of these tumours are described: adult (95%) and juvenile (5%) [1]. Juvenile ovarian granulosa tumors in most cases are secretory and hyperstrogenetic and are considered tumors with low malignant potential [8]. We describe a rare case of an impressively large juvenile granulosa cell tumor in a

15-year-old adolescent girl, the rarity of such a neoplasm suggesting the need to confront imaging data, surgical treatment aspects and histopathological findings.

Patient C., aged 15, was admitted with a 12-month history of periodic abdominal pain, abdominal enlargement and amenorrhea. Menarche from 14 years of age, previously normal menstrual cycle, sexually active since 14 years of age, which led the patient to believe she was pregnant.

On hospitalization, abdominal ultrasound examination revealed a major abdominal formation. CT imaging data with intravenous contrast allowed visualizing in the anterior compartment of the small pelvis, intraperitoneal with cranial extension in the projection of

the mesogastrium and bilateral flanks a massive, poly-septate, polylobed cystic formation of a polygonal configuration, measuring 24.0cm x 20.0cm x 10.6cm. The formation, which had a non-homogeneous structure with a well-defined outline, showed a mixed fluid-cystic content, associated with the presence of multiple intrastromal vessels, without postcontrast pathological

enlargement, pronounced mass effect exerted by compression and dislocation of abdominal and pelvic organs, bladder compression, bulging of the anterior abdominal wall. Signs of moderate accumulation of free fluid in the intraperitoneal space (with density +12UH). Ovaries and fallopian tubes were definitely not determined (fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

Patient C., 15 years old. Preoperative intravenous contrast-enhanced computed tomography - CT imaging data suggestive of the presence of a solid-cystic volume formation located in the bilateral adnexal projection with extension into the abdominal cavity, possibly yolk sac tumor of the left ovary? (explanation in text)

Detailed general blood test data found hemoglobin – 76g/l, ert- $4.20 \cdot 10^6$ /ul, hematocrit-27.0%, leukocytes-8,9%, ESR 22mm/h, while all biochemical parameters were within normal limits. Preoperative serum alpha-fetoprotein and lactate dehydrogenase levels were within the reference values.

After preoperative preparation, surgery was performed with a left transrectal laparotomy. On revision, a massive tumor formation was found, originating from the left ovary without involving adjacent organs and anatomical structures (fig. 2A). Radical resection of the tumor was performed with the fallopian tube (fig. 2B).

Fig. 2.

Intraoperative appearance of the tumor formation (A) and appearance of the resection piece in section (B)

Review of the pelvic organs revealed up to 50 ml of serous fluid in the abdominal cavity. The parietal peritoneum was without any changes, the regional lymph nodes were enlarged. Uterus and right adnexa were without pathological changes, of normal size. The operation was completed with drainage of the pelvic space and reconstitution of the anatomical plane.

The results of histopathological examination established the presence of juvenile type granulosa tumor, provisional stage pT1a, high mitotic activity (mitotic rate 40 in 10 fields of view), moderate nuclear atypia and extensive foci of necrosis. The tumor infiltrated tubular tissue in which foci of necrosis and tumor foci of juvenile type granulosa cells were present.

The patient was discharged in satisfactory condition and referred to an oncology institution to determine further treatment tactics.

Discussion. Juvenile granulosa cell tumors are rare neoplasms, usually diagnosed before the age of 20 years, predominantly in the age range 3-13 years. In some cases this tumor can be seen in girls as young as 1 year old or even diagnosed prenatally [3, 9]. The etiopathogenesis of juvenile type granulosa cell tumors is not known, unlike the adult type where the pathogenesis of this neoplasm is determined by mutations in the FOXL2 gene [14, 18]. Associations of juvenile granuloma tumors with some pathologies such as Ollier endochondromatosis [12], Maffucci syndrome have been described [17].

More commonly, in prepubertal girls, these tumours manifest as early pseudopuberty associated with isosexual development. In some cases patients may also present with contrasexual development, with signs of excessive androgenism. However, the most common symptoms are abdominal pain and abdominal distention [2, 5, 16]. In comparison to adult granulosa cell tumors, juvenile forms are characterized by a high mitotic index and comparatively more aggressive growth [7], which is also documented in our case. Granulosa cell tumours secrete steroid hormones, mainly oestrogens and less commonly androgens and progestins, while some authors have also found secretion of prolactin and insulin. Most granuloma cell tumours secrete inhibin, which is used as a tumour-specific marker for granuloma cells [6]. Evaluation of tumor markers such as α -

fetoprotein and β -HCG is important to exclude germ cell tumors [2].

The management of granuloma cell tumours depends on age and disease outcome. Surgical treatment is the primary option, with fertility-preserving procedures preferred in the early stages of the disease. Unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy is the procedure of choice in cases of stage IA tumour, also performed in our case described. Some authors consider adjuvant chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy to be necessary in advanced stage tumours [7, 11].

Staging according to the clinical picture, surgical findings and histopathological results is an important prognostic factor [15]. Juvenile granulosa cell tumour of the ovary diagnosed at an early stage has a favourable prognosis. Relapses are uncommon but usually occur within the first year. Long-term follow-up should be considered, especially in advanced forms of the disease, as some authors describe the development of late relapses [4, 19].

Conclusion. Granulosa cell tumour of the ovary is a rare neoplasm in children, characterised by aggressive growth over short periods of time, which can pose certain preoperative diagnostic problems. Although there are no standardised protocols, unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy is the preferred surgical procedure in stage IA tumour, with long-term follow-up being essential because of the risk of recurrence.

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